

JUDICIAL CONFLICT RESOLUTION IN ENGLISH COURTS

A Preliminary Overview

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“[The new court] makes resolution by the parties a culturally and actually normal part of civil dispute resolution, rather than something alternative to the mainstream. In short, it seeks to take the “A” out of “ADR”. That’s why I would like to see the new court called a resolution or solutions court.”

Lord Justice Briggs, *The New Online Court*, Oct 2016¹

This summary focuses on how the English courts appear to have shifted towards an increased preoccupation for settlement, particularly during the past 20 years. The focus is mainly on ordinary civil (non-family) courts, which hear cases in first instance (rather than appeals) (Part A), although similar practices can be found in criminal cases (Part B). For civil cases, the most relevant English courts are local county courts, as well as the High Court (including the Commercial Court and the Technology and Construction Court within the Queen’s Bench Division). For criminal cases, the focus is on first instance cases in Magistrates’ Courts and the Crown Court. The last section summarises the main reasons that are typically used by English scholars and policymakers in supporting settlement in civil and criminal cases.

¹ The Rt. Hon. Sir Michael Briggs, ‘The New Online Court – Affordable Dispute Resolution for All’ (Tom Sargant Memorial Lecture 2016, 18 October 2016).

PART A: JCR IN CIVIL (NON-FAMILY) COURTS

1. Data on court-related judicial conflict resolution

There are 178 county courts in England and Wales and they receive approximately 1.5 million filings annually. Out of those, only a small fraction of claims (about 15%) are actually defended, so they proceed to pre-trial. Out of those who proceed to pre-trial and are allocated to a track, about 38% eventually result in a hearing or a trial (approximately 3% of all claim filings).

Figure 1: Data on claims filed, defended, allocated and tried in county courts (based on averages between 2000 and 2015)

Although the percentage of claims defended and allocated to track has slowly increased throughout the past 15 years, the percentage of trials per allocated claim has slowly decreased (from 50% in 2000 to almost 30% in 2015).² In contrast, about 17,000 claims are filled in annually in the Queen’s Bench Division of the High Court.³ Only 6% of these claims proceed to trial on average.⁴

² UK Ministry of Justice, ‘Civil Justice Statistics Quarterly, England and Wales: October to December 2015’ (2016)

<https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/507771/civil-justice-statistics-october-december-2015.pdf> accessed 21 May 2016.

³ Out of which 1,000 in the Commercial Court and about 500 in the Technology and Construction Court.

⁴ UK Ministry of Justice, ‘Judicial and Court Statistics (Annual) 2011’ (2012)

<<https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/judicial-and-court-statistics-annual>>.

Figure 3 and Figure 3 below present the evolution of the number of trials or hearings in English county courts between 2000 and 2015. Figure 3 presents the raw numbers of claims/hearings. But the trend becomes even clearer in Figure 3, when we take into consideration that the ratio of claims defended from the total number of claims filed (in blue) has slowly increased throughout the years (and is forecasted to increase), while the ratio of hearings and trials to the total number of allocations (in green) has decreased (Figure 3). This suggests that the decreasing number of trials is not due to a lower number of claims entering the court system.

Figure 3: Hearings and trials in civil (non-family) County Court cases in England and Wales 2000-2015

Figure 3: Percentage defended claims (blue) and percent allocated claims gone to trial (green) brought forward from previous stage (County Court)

In 2004, Kritzer completed an informative review of judicial statistics in England and Wales, covering all data issued between 1958 and 2002.⁵ His review was based on archived judicial statistics. Figures 3 and 5 from his article are reproduced below. Figure 3 focuses on civil cases in High Court (Queen’s Bench Division),⁶ while Figure 5 focuses on civil cases in county courts.

⁵ Herbert M Kritzer, ‘Disappearing Trials - A Comparative Perspective’ (2004) 1 Journal of Empirical Legal Studies 735.

⁶ “However, even before these changes were adopted, a decline in the number of trials had begun, and well before the changes, the drop in the percentage of cases going to trial had started.” (about High Court trials, *ibid* 742.)

Figure 4: Kritzer's mapping of civil trials in the High Court (Queen's Bench Division) between 1957 and 2000.⁷

Figure 3: Trials as percentages of proceedings initiated and cases set down for trial, Queen's Bench Division of the High Court.

NOTE: "Set down for trial" refers to cases being ready for trial.

SOURCE: Lord Chancellor's Department, *Judicial Statistics, England and Wales*, various years.

⁷ *ibid* 741.

Figure 5: Kritzer's mapping of the number of trials in county courts. The second figure distinguishes small claims hearings from the rest of the trials.⁸

Figure 5: Number of trials in the County Courts, 1967–2003. (a) Small claims and other cases combined. (b) Small claims and other cases separately.

⁸ *ibid* 746.

Both figures seem to reveal a downward trend of civil trials, except for county court small claim hearings, which have increased since 1990, presumably due to the increase of small claims threshold. Kritzer attempted to account for the major changes in the patterns by analysing the structural reforms that took place throughout the period analysed. He nevertheless pointed out that the vanishing trial phenomenon has had a downward trend before and somehow independent of these changes.

With regards to specific data on court settlement practices, Kritzer complained that

Specifically, three categories, "settled during course of trial or hearing," "settled at door of court," and "approval of prior settlement given" were collapsed into a single category labeled "settled during course of trial or hearing," with a footnote explaining that this was a combination of prior separate categories. Efforts to obtain unaggregated figures from the Lord Chancellor's Department (renamed the Department for Constitutional Affairs in 2003) were unsuccessful.⁹

Even so, the new statistics (issued from 2000 onwards) are even less informative than the old statistics. The new statistics explain that only a percentage of cases get to allocation or trial due to withdrawal or settlement, but they don't actually distinguish between the two in their datasets.¹⁰

In fact, publicly-available statistics have numerous times been criticised by academic researchers¹¹ and judges¹² alike for not providing more specific information about the settlement of cases or about what happens to the majority of cases, for claims that are not defended, not allocated or do not go to trial. In 1998, in his major review of the County Court Small Claims, Baldwin was pointing out that the published judicial statistics did not give any information on small claims specifically, especially regarding the 95% of the claims that went undefended and received a default judgment.¹³ Baldwin thought that this was due to the fact that "the defendant pays up or makes an offer of

⁹ *ibid* 738 n16.

¹⁰ Yet in his study of the Mayor's and City of London Court, Simon Roberts claims that 62% of defended claims are *settled* before being allocated (Simon Roberts, *A Court in the City: Commercial Litigation in London at the Beginning of the 21st Century* (1 edition, Wildy, Simmonds & Hill 2013) 114.).

¹¹ John Baldwin, *Small Claims in the County Courts in England and Wales: The Bargain Basement of Civil Justice?* (Clarendon Press 1997) 21; Hazel Genn, 'Court-Based ADR Initiatives for Non-Family Civil Disputes' (2002) 21-2.

¹² Rupert M Jackson, 'Review of Civil Litigation Costs' (TSO 2010) 45.

¹³ Baldwin (n 11) 21.

payment to the plaintiff” and “the parties do not trouble to inform the court” about their settlement.¹⁴

In a similar vein, Lord Jackson pointed out that there is an even greater number of “unissued claims” – claims which are settled before being filed in court – which by definition are not included in the Judicial Statistics. Lord Jackson argued that these unissued claims are nonetheless very important in understanding the settlement phenomenon, because “the settlements negotiated in respect of unissued claims and the costs incurred in achieving such settlements are governed by the parties’ expectation of what would happen in the event of litigation”.¹⁵ In his Review of Litigation Costs, he relied on Legal Aid figures,¹⁶ data from liability insurers, figures from the Compensation Recovery Unit¹⁷ and the Fourth UK Bodily Injury Awards Study¹⁸ in order to get a rough sense of settlements that take place before claims are filed in court.¹⁹

Notwithstanding the lack of relevant settlement-related variables in public statistical reports, an analysis of court files could in principle reveal more information about the rate of settlement in English courts. Baldwin was pleasantly surprised “to discover how much useful information could be unearthed simply by reading through court documents.”²⁰ Other researchers such as Genn discovered that court files are much less informative with regards to settlement practices, and pointed out how time-consuming and difficult it is to actually access the needed information:

Unlike some other jurisdictions where information about court cases is more readily (and electronically) available, answering even relatively straightforward questions about the outcome of English civil cases is complicated and time consuming. Although information about trials is generally easily ascertainable from court paper files, it is often impossible in the absence of trial information to establish whether the

¹⁴ *ibid* 21 n3.

¹⁵ Jackson (n 12) 62.

¹⁶ UK Ministry of Justice, ‘Legal Aid Statistics Quarterly: January to March 2016’ (2016) <https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/533178/legal-aid-statistics-england-and-wales-bulletin-jan-to-mar_16.pdf> accessed 25 July 2016.

¹⁷ Department for Work and Pensions, ‘Compensation Recovery Unit Performance Data’ (2016) <<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/compensation-recovery-unit-performance-data>> accessed 25 July 2016.

¹⁸ International Underwriting Association of London, *The Fourth UK Bodily Injury Awards Study* (International Underwriting Association of London 2007).

¹⁹ Jackson (n 12) 60.

²⁰ Baldwin (n 11) 24.

case has settled, and if so how, whether it is still live, or whether the claim has died. Most importantly for this particular study [...] there was no way of discerning from paper files whether, following the making of an ADR Order by the Court, any ADR procedure had been used.²¹

Since 2010 the new governmental platform *data.gov.uk* offers open access to governmental data to the wider public. Perhaps more importantly, it also mentions the datasets that are not publicly-available, but are nonetheless maintained by English courts and could in principle be accessed by researchers with prior permission. For research on settlement, CaseMan is the case management system currently used in County Courts; CE File System is recently launched for High Court cases; Libra is used in Magistrates' Courts; and CREST is used by the Crown Court. In addition, some court listings can be found online, either on Court Serve or on the Ministry of Justice website.

2. Reforms that encourage settlement in English civil justice

During the past two decades, the United Kingdom has made significant progress in shifting the role of courts to a more settlement-oriented approach. In 1996, at the request of the Lord Chancellor, Lord Woolf wrote the *Access to Justice* report with the aim of consolidating the current rules of procedure.²² One of the core themes of the report "has been the need to bring the uncontrolled features of the adversarial system under proper discipline. Another has been to promote more, better and earlier settlements."²³ As consequence, the report recommended the introduction of wide case management powers of the court, in order to control the cost of litigation for both parties and the state and to encourage settlement anytime during the proceedings.

Woolf's recommendations were swiftly integrated in the 1998 Civil Procedure Rules (CPR). For the first time in British jurisprudence, the court had gained a duty to actively manage cases in view of ensuring justice proportionally to costs ("the overriding objective"). Managing the case actively means that the British judge now must "encourage the parties to co-operate with each other in the conduct of the

²¹ Genn, 'Court-Based ADR Initiatives for Non-Family Civil Disputes' (n 11) 21–2.

²² Lord Woolf, 'Access to Justice' (1996)
<<http://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/+http://www.dca.gov.uk/civil/final/contents.htm>>
accessed 25 November 2015.

²³ *ibid* 9.1.

proceedings”,²⁴ to “encourage the parties to use an alternative dispute resolution procedure if the court considers that appropriate” and “facilitate the use of such procedure”,²⁵ as well as actively “helping the parties to settle the whole or part of the case”.²⁶ In other words, the current CPR gave a wide remit to the judge to attempt settlement: the judge is not just supposed to encourage parties to use out-of-court settlement methods, but he also must facilitate settlement himself. In all instances, the role of the judge has shifted from that of a passive umpire of adversarial conflict to an active facilitator of dispute resolution.²⁷

A second major innovation introduced in the 1998 CPR influenced by Woolf was the introduction of pre-action protocols. The pre-action protocols direct parties on the steps they are required to make before coming to court. An important pre-action step is to attempt to settle the matter. The court expects that the parties have first attempted to settle the matter before going to court, including using ADR services to help them in settlement.²⁸ When filing a claim in court, the parties need to indicate the steps they have taken to settle the claim, and why those failed.²⁹ British judges can use two mechanisms to enforce compliance with pre-action protocols: (1) they can stay the case until the parties have complied with the protocols;³⁰ and (2) they can sanction the parties for non-compliance with increased litigation costs.³¹

Settlement is not encouraged just during the pre-filing phase. A third major innovation of the 1998 Civil Procedure Rules was the introduction of Part 36 *Offers to Settle*.³² Part 36 Offers give parties the opportunity to attempt a settlement of the dispute at any point during litigation. If Part 36 Offers are made during the trial, the content of the offers is withheld from the judge whether they are accepted or not. But if the trial comes

²⁴ The Civil Procedure Rules 1998 1999 s 1.2.(2).(a).

²⁵ *ibid* 1.2.(2).(e).

²⁶ *ibid* 1.2.(2).(f).

²⁷ “By giving the mandate to the judges that they ‘must further the overriding objective by *actively* managing cases’, the reactive approach to civil litigation was replaced by the proactive intervention as required by the CPR.” (Deirdre Dwyer (ed), *The Civil Procedure Rules Ten Years On* (Oxford University Press 2010) <<https://global.oup.com/academic/product/the-civil-procedure-rules-ten-years-on-9780199576883>> accessed 20 May 2016.)

²⁸ Practice Direction: Pre-Action Conduct and Protocols s 3.

²⁹ ‘N150 Allocation Questionnaire - Civil Claims’ <http://www.daviesolicitors.co.uk/forms_davies/Civil%20Disputes/Allocation%20Questionnaire.pdf> accessed 26 November 2015.

³⁰ The Civil Procedure Rules 1998 (n 24).

³¹ *ibid* 44.3; Practice Direction: Pre-Action Conduct and Protocols (n 28).

³² Part 36 - Offers to Settle 2015 (Civil Procedure Rules) pt. 36.

to an end through a judgment, the judge can compare the final damages awarded with the Part 36 Offers made, in his costs decision.³³

A host of landmark cases decided by English courts between 1999 and 2008 show that these judicial dispute resolution instruments are taken seriously and employed by the English judges in their decision-making. In 2001 in *Cowl*, parties were specifically encouraged by the Court of Appeal to avoid litigation.³⁴ In 2002, *Dunnett* showed that even if a party wins in court, it could still get cost sanctions from the judge if they unreasonably refused ADR.³⁵ In 2003, the High Court took a further step, by sanctioning a government department for unreasonably refusing mediation, even though the party believed there was a point of law to be settled in court, and that point of law was indeed admitted and resolved by the court.³⁶ This case was particularly important given that in 2001 the UK Government had made a pledge whereby all governmental departments and agencies would first make recourse to ADR before attempting litigation.³⁷ The pledge was renewed in 2011 through the Dispute Resolution Commitment.³⁸

2004 marked a temporary U-turn in judicial encouragement of settlement, through the *Halsey* case. The Court of Appeal decided that compulsion to send parties to mediation was against the right to a fair trial stipulated in section 6 of the European Human Rights Convention (thus overturning *Cowl* and similar decisions); yet it maintained that cost sanctions could still be imposed on parties if they unreasonably refuse ADR.³⁹ Despite *Halsey*, in 2008 *Malmesbury* continued the trend towards a wider power of judges to encourage and sanction parties to settle; it ruled that cost penalties could also be imposed on parties that have an unreasonable behaviour *during* mediation.⁴⁰ This marked an increase in the judges' discretion to evaluate and encourage settlement efforts of parties, even when the efforts take place out of court.

³³ The Civil Procedure Rules 1998 (n 24); 'A Part 36 offer will be treated as "without prejudice except as to costs"'. Part 36 - Offers to Settle (n 32).

³⁴ *Cowl and Others v Plymouth City Council* [2001] EWCA Civ 1935X 1935 (England and Wales Court of Appeal (Civil Division)).

³⁵ *Dunnett v Railtrack Plc (Costs)* [2002] EWCA Civ 303 (EWCA (Civ)).

³⁶ *Royal Bank of Canada Trust Corporation Ltd v Secretary of State for Defence* [2003] UKHC.

³⁷ UK Government, '2001 UK Government Pledge on ADR' (2001) <<http://uk.practicallaw.com/1-385-1394#>> accessed 21 April 2016.

³⁸ UK Ministry of Justice, The Dispute Resolution Commitment 2011.

³⁹ *Halsey v Milton Keynes General NHS Trust* [2004] EWCA Civ 576.

⁴⁰ *Earl of Malmesbury v Strutt & Parker* [2008] EWHC 424 (QB) (Queen's Bench Division).

2.1. Court-based mediation schemes

The first decade following the Woolf reforms was also marked by the implementation and evaluation of several court-based schemes created to encourage settlement. In 1998 Genn evaluated the first voluntary mediation pilot scheme called the Central London County Court Mediation Scheme, which ran between 1996 and 1998.⁴¹ Genn analysed 1,100 court files from cases that went through mediation, cases that were invited but refused mediation, and cases that were not invited to mediation. She supplemented the quantitative analysis with mediation observations and interviews with litigants, lawyers and mediators. Genn discovered that mediation was accepted in very few cases (5%; virtually none in personal injury cases), but the settlement rates were significantly higher (62% vs 47%) than in cases not included in the mediation scheme.

Four years later, Genn published another evaluation of newly-established settlement practices, this time in the High Court. In her 2002 report, she focused on the ADR Orders made by judges in the Commercial Court between July 1996 and June 2000.⁴² Genn discovered a significant difference between cases where the parties decided to follow the ADR Order and cases where they did not follow. Although in both categories disputes eventually settled in more than 60% of cases, significantly less cases that had followed an ADR Order actually ended up going to trial (5% compared to 15% who did not follow the order). The figure below summarises these findings:

⁴¹ Hazel Genn, 'The Central London County Court Mediation Scheme: Evaluation Report' (1998) <http://www.cnmd.ac.uk/laws/judicial-institute/files/Central_London_County_Court_Mediation_Scheme.pdf> accessed 22 June 2016.

⁴² Genn, 'Court-Based ADR Initiatives for Non-Family Civil Disputes' (n 11).

Figure 6: Case outcomes for claims given ADR Orders (Genn 2002)

In addition, over time “a substantially *higher* proportion of cases were leading to ADR procedures being used than at the beginning of the review period”.⁴³ The parties involved generally thought that the judicial ADR Order had a positive or neutral impact, by opening communication between parties and creating a neutral ground for negotiation. But the parties also considered that other factors had an important impact on the success of the Order (the timing of the order, the type of case, or the amount of administrative support).⁴⁴

The same year (2002), Goriely, Moorhead and Abrams conducted a major qualitative study, focused on whether 54 lawyers, insurers and claims managers “thought that the reforms had resulted in a less adversarial ‘culture of litigation’, which put greater emphasis on settlement and co-operation”.⁴⁵ Surprisingly, they discovered that although the Woolf reforms had positive consequences such as providing clearer litigation structures and “soft” improvement in “the level of co-operation and settlement”, it had not resolved the problem of costs; costs had actually increased (by 11% vs 8% inflation), most likely due to front-loading. These findings were replicated by Peysner and Seneviratne in 2005 in a qualitative study with a wide range of judges,

⁴³ *ibid* 30–1.

⁴⁴ *ibid* ii–v.

⁴⁵ Tamara Goriely and others, ‘More Civil Justice? The Impact of the Woolf Reforms on Pre-Action Behaviour’ (Law Society 2002) xi.

court officials and practitioners from 8 county courts across England.⁴⁶ Although the overall sentiment was that the culture of litigation “had changed for the better”, and that “co-operation between the parties, and between the parties and the courts, had improved”, that wasn’t translated into a cut of expenses or of delay. In addition, although the settlement rate had increased and this was thought of as a consequence of the Woolf reforms, the majority of cases settled were done so pre-issue and not as a consequence of ADR being incorporated in the court process.⁴⁷

A wider governmental initiative to test various models of court-led settlement across England and Wales was launched post-Woolf, following the first few pilots. Initially, these were local court-sponsored mediation schemes, which were designed to offer low-cost (or free), time-limited (~3 hrs; additional time permitted) mediation held on the court premises after the end of the normal court day. The courts administered the schemes, but the mediators were not judges, they were certified mediators picked from a list. In some schemes, a member of the court acted as a clerk. In all schemes, mediation was voluntary and had to be agreed by both parties; the judge was entitled to encourage parties to attempt mediation, according to the CPR; in very few courts, a compulsory ADR Order was piloted.⁴⁸

These court-based mediation pilots resulted in a flurry of academic reports evaluating each of these pilots: Doyle evaluated the Small Claims Mediation Service at Manchester County Court (2006);⁴⁹ Webley et al evaluated the Birmingham Mediation Scheme (2006);⁵⁰ Prince and Belcher evaluated the court-based mediation processes in Exeter and Guildford (2006);⁵¹ Genn et al reviewed the first Automatic Referral to Mediation scheme (as well as the voluntary mediation scheme), which had been launched in the Central London County Court in 2004 and 1996 respectively (2007);⁵² Gould focused on

⁴⁶ John Peysner and Mary Seneviratne, ‘The Management of Civil Cases: The Courts and Post-Woolf Landscape’ (Department for Constitutional Affairs 2005).

⁴⁷ *ibid* 2.

⁴⁸ Hazel Genn and others, *Twisting Arms: Court Referred and Court Linked Mediation Under Judicial Pressure* (Ministry of Justice 2007).

⁴⁹ Margaret Doyle, ‘Evaluation of the Small Claims Mediation Service at Manchester County Court’ [2006] Dept of Constitutional Affairs, London.

⁵⁰ Lisa Webley, Pamela Abrams and Sylvie Bacquet, ‘Evaluation of the Birmingham Court-Based Civil (Non-Family) Mediation Scheme’ (Social Science Research Network 2006) SSRN Scholarly Paper ID 1349874 <<http://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=1349874>> accessed 21 May 2016.

⁵¹ Sue Prince and Sophie Belcher, ‘An Evaluation of the Effectiveness of Court-Based Mediation Processes in Non-Family Civil Proceedings at Exeter and Guildford County Courts’ (Department of Constitutional Affairs 2006) <<https://ore.exeter.ac.uk/repository/handle/10036/22735>> accessed 13 June 2016.

⁵² Genn and others (n 48).

the use of mediation in the Technology and Construction Court in London, Birmingham and Bristol (2009);⁵³ and Roberts on the Mayor's and City of London Court (2013).⁵⁴ Each of these studies typically involved quantitative and qualitative analysis of case files (of cases that had been invited to mediation, both those who accepted and those who refused); and qualitative interviews or surveys with litigants, their representatives, judges, and court staff.

These pilots revealed that (1) generally, cases who underwent mediation were more likely to settle;⁵⁵ (2) that judicial involvement or judicial directions were a significant incentive,⁵⁶ but only in voluntary schemes;⁵⁷ (3) that telephone mediation slowly became more used than face-to-face mediation;⁵⁸ and (4) that mediation had overall saved 'judicial time',⁵⁹ although it increased 'admin time' and delayed the progress of cases when unsuccessful.⁶⁰ When interviewed, solicitors identified costs and time savings as main incentives for the parties to use mediation schemes.⁶¹ Gould's study also identified the parts of the litigation process when the parties were most likely to attempt mediation.⁶² The 'Manchester model' was considered particularly successful and thus implemented nationwide from 2007 as the Small Claims Mediation Service,⁶³ although some commentators questioned the replicability of the pilot's results.⁶⁴

⁵³ Nicholas Gould, Claire King and Aaron Hudson-Tyreman, 'The Use of Mediation in Construction Disputes: Summary Report of the Final Results' (2009).

⁵⁴ Roberts (n 10).

⁵⁵ Doyle (n 49); Genn and others (n 48); Gould, King and Hudson-Tyreman (n 53); Roberts (n 10).

⁵⁶ Doyle (n 49); Webley, Abrams and Bacquet (n 50); Prince and Belcher (n 51); Gould, King and Hudson-Tyreman (n 53).

⁵⁷ Genn and others (n 48); Prince and Belcher (n 51).

⁵⁸ Doyle (n 49).

⁵⁹ *ibid.*

⁶⁰ Genn and others (n 48).

⁶¹ Webley, Abrams and Bacquet (n 50).

⁶² Gould et al found that parties would be most likely to settle 1) during exchange of pleadings; 2) during/as result of disclosure; 3) as result of Part 36 offer to settle; 4) shortly before trial (Gould, King and Hudson-Tyreman (n 53) 16.).

⁶³ James Rustidge, 'Small Claims Mediation Service at Manchester County Court and Roll out to All HMCS Areas in England and Wales and 2007 / 2008' (2007); Her Majesty's Court Service (HMCS), 'Small Claims Mediation – Now at a Court near You!' [2007] *Out of Court Newsletter* <http://www.clerksroom.com/downloads/191-out-of-court-newsletter_may2007.pdf> accessed 30 September 2016.

⁶⁴ Ann Brady, 'Judging the Value of Mediation' *Law Society Gazette* (26 October 2007) <<http://www.lawgazette.co.uk/law/judging-the-value-of-mediation/4489.fullarticle>> accessed 30 September 2016.

Unfortunately, this is at present the only mediation offering routinely provided by the civil courts. Moreover, its budget is restricted and thus provides less than half of the mediators needed to meet the current demand.⁶⁵

The findings of these studies have led to a few major developments in the last decade. First, the unexpected success of telephone mediation led in Nov 2004 to the creation of the National Mediation Helpline.⁶⁶ The Helpline was promoted by the court, which sent information leaflets together with the allocation questionnaire; it offered advice to parties on mediation; and if both parties agreed, the helpline arranged a fixed-fee telephone mediation, facilitated by a mediator accredited by the Civil Mediation Council. Unfortunately, the Helpline was closed in 2011 and was replaced with a Civil Mediation Online Directory.⁶⁷

Second, the findings revealed that the Woolf reforms had not managed to have the intended consequences with regards to costs savings in litigation. This issue was explored by Lord Jackson in his 2009 “Review of Civil Litigation Costs”.⁶⁸ The Jackson Review was conducted because the senior judiciary was concerned at the disproportionate litigation costs, despite the implementation (and the perceived success) of the Woolf reforms. For instance, the pre-action protocols had led to a “front-loading” of costs before trial; but also, when cases settled between issue and trial, parties were likely to incur more costs than before 1999. Lord Jackson’s review looked at the impact of case management on the cost of litigation, it sought opinions of participants in the process, and it also reviewed cost practices from other jurisdictions. The report concluded that the costs system should be based on legal expenses that reflect the nature/complexity of the case, and that low value claims (“fast track”) should have a fixed fee. The final report contained an entire section dedicated to “Controlling the costs of litigation” which addressed pre-action protocols, ADR, case management,

⁶⁵ Lord Justice Briggs, ‘Civil Courts Structure Review (CCSR): Interim Report’ (2015) para 2.90 <<https://www.judiciary.gov.uk/wp-content/uploads/2016/01/ccsr-interim-report-dec-15-final1.pdf>> accessed 23 June 2016.

⁶⁶ Ministry of Justice, ‘Launch of National Mediation Helpline’ (3 January 2005) <<http://www.wired-gov.net/wg/wg-news-1.nsf/54e6de9e0c383719802572b9005141ed/74d6cceeef4805802572ab004badf9?OpenDocument>> accessed 30 September 2016.

⁶⁷ UK Government, ‘New Civil Mediation Online Directory’ (29 September 2011) <<https://www.gov.uk/government/news/new-civil-mediation-online-directory>> accessed 30 September 2016.

⁶⁸ Jackson (n 12).

cost management, disclosure and Part 36 offers, among others. The Jackson reforms resulted in a stronger encouragement of ADR and of costs management in the UK.⁶⁹

The last few years are characterised by a continued push of settlement by all state actors in the UK. In 2011, the Ministry of Justice has issued the Dispute Resolution Commitment (DRC), which aims to encourage “the increased use of flexible, creative and constructive approaches to dispute resolution” by promising that all state bodies will have a settlement-oriented approach in all their dealings with its citizens or the private sector.⁷⁰ Senior judges have also expressed their support for conflict resolution mechanisms as necessary and complementary to the traditional type of adversarial litigation.⁷¹

Nowadays, the concern for settlement in civil cases is entering a new era. In 2015, a newly-created CJC Online Dispute Resolution Advisory group published a revolutionary report advocating the power of new technologies and of online platforms to enhancing dispute resolution in the United Kingdom.⁷² Among its innovative proposals, the report proposes that the justice system should not just focus on dispute resolution, but also on prior stages of dispute avoidance and dispute containment. The Group recommends “online facilitation to support dispute containment; and online evaluation to support dispute avoidance”.⁷³ Its proposals have been further pushed by Lord Justice Briggs in his major Civil Courts Structure Review which aims to overhaul the structure of the civil justice system.⁷⁴ Briggs pushes on and discusses the implementation of the HM Online Court, commenting that the “stage 2 of the OC process is mainly directed to making conciliation a culturally normal part of the civil court process rather than, as it is at

⁶⁹ Susan Blake, Julie Browne and Stuart Sime, *The Jackson ADR Handbook* (Oxford University Press 2013) <https://books.google.co.uk/books?id=4tplIQEACAAJ&dq=jackson+adr+handbook&hl=en&sa=X&redir_esc=y> accessed 4 November 2015.

⁷⁰ UK Ministry of Justice The Dispute Resolution Commitment (n 38).

⁷¹ The Right Hon. The Lord Thomas, ‘Developing Commercial Law through the Courts: Rebalancing the Relationship between the Courts and Arbitration (The Bailii Lecture 2016)’ (9 March 2016) <<https://www.judiciary.gov.uk/announcements/speech-by-the-lord-chief-justice-the-bailii-lecture-2016/>> accessed 21 March 2016.

⁷² ODR Advisory Group, ‘Online Dispute Resolution for Low Value Civil Claims (Final Report)’ (Civil Justice Council 2015) <<https://www.judiciary.gov.uk/wp-content/uploads/2015/02/Online-Dispute-Resolution-Final-Web-Version1.pdf>> accessed 23 June 2016.

⁷³ *ibid* 17.

⁷⁴ Lord Justice Briggs, ‘Civil Courts Structure Review (CCSR): Final Report’ (2016) <<https://www.judiciary.gov.uk/wp-content/uploads/2016/07/civil-courts-structure-review-final-report-jul-16-final-1.pdf>> accessed 1 August 2016.

present, a purely optional and extraneous process, encapsulated in the 'alternative' part of the acronym ADR".⁷⁵

⁷⁵ *ibid* 6.13.

PART B: JCR IN CRIMINAL COURTS

1. Routes to settlement in criminal cases

The concept of judicial conflict resolution has a less straightforward meaning in criminal cases. Nonetheless, there are several current judicial practices that can be considered as enabling the swift resolution of criminal cases. In criminal cases, the settlement can be seen as taking place either between the defendant and the state (e.g. like in plea bargains), between the defendant and the victim (e.g. practices of restorative justice), or between the defendant and the community (e.g. practices from community courts).

Explicit judicial encouragement for alternative conflict resolution routes in criminal law can be traced back to 2001, when in his “Review of the Criminal Courts of England and Wales”, Sir Robin Auld recommended a range of methods and reforms, beginning with the development and implementation “of a national strategy to ensure consistent, appropriate and effective use of restorative justice techniques across England and Wales”.⁷⁶ Auld recommended a move “to cooperation between the parties according to standard time-tables, wherever necessary, seeking written directions from the court” and he argued that restorative justice and “diversionary mechanisms” can be attempted at various stages in the criminal process.⁷⁷ In addition, Sir Auld gave the DVLA out-of-court settlement scheme as a case of good practice,⁷⁸ recommended the introduction of fixed penalty notices for traffic offences,⁷⁹ and of a conditional cautioning scheme for minor offences.⁸⁰ With regards to settlement methods in court, the Auld review recommended the introduction of sentence discounts for early pleas, and the reintroduction of advance sentence indications by judges⁸¹.

Unlike Woolf, despite proposing a range of restorative justice and alternative criminal justice reforms, Sir Auld considered that “there is no persuasive case for a general move away from the adversarial process”⁸², but he opposed the adversarial process to the civil jurisdiction model of the inquisitorial process, rather than to a concept of settlement.

⁷⁶ Sir Robin Auld, ‘Review of the Criminal Courts of England and Wales’ (2001) 391.

⁷⁷ *ibid* 23.

⁷⁸ *ibid* 731.

⁷⁹ *ibid* 375.

⁸⁰ *ibid* 382.

⁸¹ *ibid* 434–444.

⁸² *ibid* 16.

The success of the Woolf review in subsequently codifying the Civil Procedure Rules inspired Auld to advocate a similar codification and consolidation of criminal procedure rules, which at that time consisted in no less than 271 normative acts and many more non-statutory common law sources of practice.⁸³ A result of the Auld Review was the creation of the Criminal Procedure Rules Committee in 2003,⁸⁴ which by 2005 managed to publish the first version of the Criminal Procedure Rules (CrPR).⁸⁵ In their first iteration, the CrPR were only an orderly consolidation of existing legislation, but the Overriding Principle of criminal justice and practical principles of Case Management were formulated for the first time, very similarly to their counterparts in the Civil Procedure Rules. Since 2010, the CrPRs have been amended manually.

In 2015, Sir Brian Leveson conducted another major review of the criminal justice system. His “Review of Efficiency in Criminal Proceedings” stipulates a third overarching principle of criminal proceedings, the “Duty of Direct Engagement”.⁸⁶ According to the duty of direct engagement, both identified representatives in a criminal case have a duty to engage with each other, and agree at the earliest opportunity (well before any first hearing) on “relevant matters”, e.g. charges, evidence, agenda for the trial etc.

Sir Leveson also supported the implementation of a “National Early Guilty Plea (EGP)” scheme, whereby guilty pleas would be elicited “in an efficient manner by producing the most effective opportunities for those who are guilty to plead at the earliest stage” and thus would reduce the number of hearings in Crown Courts.⁸⁷

Just like in the civil justice system, the criminal justice system (CJS) is also preparing for a major overhaul through the massive digitisation of court-related processes. This overhaul was advocated by Sir Leveson through the initiation of the CJS Common Platform,⁸⁸ which is now running nationally. For instance, there is now a fully-implemented online plea filing system for minor offences in Magistrates’ Courts.⁸⁹

⁸³ *ibid* 508.

⁸⁴ Courts Act 2003 s 69.

⁸⁵ The Criminal Procedure Rules 2005 2005.

⁸⁶ The Rt Hon Sir Brian Leveson, ‘Review of Efficiency in Criminal Proceedings’ (2015) ch 2.3. Duty of Direct Engagement <<https://www.judiciary.gov.uk/wp-content/uploads/2015/01/review-of-efficiency-in-criminal-proceedings-20151.pdf>> accessed 25 July 2016.

⁸⁷ *ibid* 7.1 National Early Guilty Plea (‘EGP’) scheme.

⁸⁸ *ibid* 1.4 The CJS Common Platform.

⁸⁹ ‘Online Plea – from Development to Live | Inside HMCTS’ <<https://insidehmcts.blog.gov.uk/2016/11/30/online-plea-from-development-to-live/>> accessed 13 December 2016.

The next section presents a few conflict resolution practices specific to the British criminal justice system. Some conflict resolution practices are available to the state actors before even the case goes in front of the judge. The best examples are the out of court disposals and the prosecutorial public interest test.

1.1. Out of court disposals

Out of court disposals are not new – they have been used for many years in minor traffic offences such as parking fines and minor speeding offences. The Police and Criminal Evidence Act 1984 introduced cautions by police inspectors.⁹⁰ Out of court disposals are used by the police to deal with very minor, first-time offences which do not merit prosecution at court. *Most out of court disposals require the offender to admit guilt and agree with the disposal.*

There are several types of out of court disposals available to police officers:

- **Cannabis warnings** – warning is given for offenders caught with an amount of cannabis for personal use; drug is confiscated, a warning is made on the local systems, but it does not amount to a conviction and it cannot be considered an aggravating factor;⁹¹
- **Penalty notices for disorder and fixed penalty notices** – introduced by the Criminal Justice and Police Act 2001 as “on-the-spot fines” for specific order-related (such as shoplifting, disorderly behaviour, drunken behaviour etc.) or traffic-related disorders.⁹² The offender has 21 days to pay or appeal the notice in court. *Therefore, for this type of disposal, the offender does not have to admit guilt*, but the police are required to have sufficient evidence to support the charge.⁹³

⁹⁰ Police and Criminal Evidence Act 1984 1984.

⁹¹ Sentencing Council, ‘Out of Court Disposals’ <<https://www.sentencingcouncil.org.uk/explanatory-material/item/out-of-court-disposals/>> accessed 21 September 2016.

⁹² Sentencing Council, ‘7. Offences for Which Penalty Notices Are Available’ <<https://www.sentencingcouncil.org.uk/explanatory-material/item/out-of-court-disposals/7-offences-for-which-penalty-notices-are-available/>> accessed 21 November 2016.

⁹³ Crown Prosecution Service, ‘Cautioning and Diversion: Legal Guidance’ <http://www.cps.gov.uk/legal/a_to_c/cautioning_and_diversion/> accessed 21 November 2016.

- **Simple cautions** – introduced by the Criminal Justice Act 2003⁹⁴; can be given “where there is evidence that the offender has committed an offence, the offender admits to the offence, it is not in the public interest to prosecute and the offender agrees to being given the caution”.⁹⁵ That said, the caution is not considered a conviction, so although it is recorded in the criminal record, it is not necessarily an aggravating factor in subsequent charges. Cautions are available for both summary and indictable offences, but for the latter the CPS must be consulted.
- **Conditional cautions** – unlike simple cautions, conditional cautions have rehabilitative, reparative, or financially punitive conditions attached to them. If the conditions are not fulfilled, the offender can be charged with the initial offence.
- **Youth cautions** – formally introduced by section 135 of the Legal Aid, Sentencing and Punishment of Offenders Act 2012 to specifically adapt the regime of cautions to the youth justice system.
- **Restorative justice** – the officer can decide to bring together the offender and the harmed parties/victims in a restorative justice process and thus enable everyone affected by a particular incident to play a part in repairing the harm and finding a positive way forward. A “level 1” restorative justice procedure can be done “on the street” by the officer himself; or he can refer the parties to a “level 2” restorative justice conference, as alternative or in addition to a CJS procedure.⁹⁶ Restorative justice conferences are led by trained facilitators and overseen by the Restorative Justice Council.⁹⁷

The following figure, extracted from the Criminal Justice Quarterly published by the Ministry of Justice, presents the amount of out of court disposals in contrast to the amount of prosecutions taken through the Magistrates’ Courts between 2005 and 2015.⁹⁸

⁹⁴ Criminal Justice Act 2003 2003.

⁹⁵ Sentencing Council (n 91).

⁹⁶ Association of Chief Police Officers (ACPO), Restorative Justice Guidance and Minimum Standards 2011 7.

⁹⁷ ‘Restorative Justice Council Website’ <<http://restorativejustice.org.uk/>> accessed 23 November 2016.

⁹⁸ UK Ministry of Justice, ‘Criminal Justice Statistics Quarterly - June 2015’ (2015).

Figure 7: Number of offenders dealt with by out of court disposals and magistrates' courts respectively, from 2005 until 2015 (apud Criminal Justice Quarterly – June 2015).

Figure 1.2: Individuals dealt with formally by the CJS⁴, 12 months ending June 2005 to 12 months ending June 2015

Two aspects are visible from the figure above. First, that out of about 1.8 million criminal justice proceedings per year, only about 18% constitute out of court disposals, and this ratio has apparently systematically decreased throughout the past decade.⁹⁹ Second, that the amount of criminal proceedings going through courts has remained remarkably stable, which might suggest that out of court disposals had no significant impact on diminishing court proceedings.

The Ministry of Justice figures also suggest that cautions are the most utilised out of court disposal method (57%), followed by community resolutions (35%), penalty notices for disorder (29%) and cannabis/khat warnings (20%).¹⁰⁰

The figure below displays how the amount of different types of out of court disposals evolved in time. It reveals that both penalty notices for disorder and cautions have continuously decreased over the past decade, for all types of offences.¹⁰¹

⁹⁹ For instance, between 22% in 2011 to 14% in 2015. These averages were computed from data between 2011 and 2015 (ibid Overview table Q1.1.).

¹⁰⁰ ibid Overview table Q1.1.

Figure 8: Decrease of cautions and penalty notice for disorders for all categories of offenders, from 2005 to 2015.

The large diversity of out of court disposals puts police officers in a situation akin to a sentencing magistrate. To assess whether an out of court disposal is appropriate or not, and which one, the police officer must assess the severity of the purported offence. In order to assist police officers in selecting appropriate out of court disposals, the Association of Chief Police Officers (ACPO) has published a Gravity Factors Matrix.¹⁰²

For summary offences, the police officer does not have to ask for permission from the public prosecutor to apply an out of court disposal. For indictable offences (those

¹⁰¹ ibid Overview tables Q2.1 and Q2.2.

¹⁰² Not publicly available. Crown Prosecution Service, 'Cautioning and Diversion' (n 93).

normally triable in the Crown Court), the situation is different: the police officer can consider an out of court disposal (e.g. a caution), but he has to first refer it to the Crown Prosecution Service.

Full guidance on when and how police officers should or should not refer a case to the prosecution can be found in the latest edition of “The Director’s Guidance on Charging”, issued in 2013 by the Director of Public Prosecutions.¹⁰³ According to the guide, police officers have the responsibility of “diverting, charging and referring cases as directed” and of “assessing cases before referral to ensure the Full Code or Threshold Test can be met on the available evidence as appropriate to the circumstances of the case”.¹⁰⁴

1.2. Prosecution: the public interest criterion

Both police officers and prosecutors have the power to decide whether an offence should be proceeded against in court, or “settled” otherwise. Depending on the severity of the offence, the decision is either taken by the police officer (e.g. for summary offences) or the prosecutor (e.g. for indictable offences).

In order for a case to go to court, it has to pass the Full Code Test.¹⁰⁵ The Full Code Test has two stages: (1) the evidential stage; and (2) the public interest stage. The evidential stage requires that enough evidence was gathered, according to the rules of evidence, to provide “a realistic prospect of conviction” for each defendant for each charge.¹⁰⁶ But perhaps more importantly, the charge does not just be based on evidence – it also has to be in accordance with “the public interest”. The public interest stage determines the prosecution to consider whether it really is in the public interest for the case to be pursued in court. The Code for Crown Prosecutor and the DPP’s Guidance on Charging provide a comprehensive list of factors that the prosecution must take into account when deciding if the charge passes the public interest test. These factors are:

1. Seriousness of the offence;
2. Culpability of the suspect;
3. Circumstances of the offence and the harm caused to the victim;

¹⁰³ Director of Public Prosecutions, *The Director’s Guidance On Charging 2013 (5th Ed): Guidance to Police Officers and Crown Prosecutors Issued by the Director of Public Prosecution under S37A of the Police and Criminal Evidence Act 1984* 2013.

¹⁰⁴ *ibid* 2.

¹⁰⁵ *ibid* 8.

¹⁰⁶ Crown Prosecution Service, *Code for Crown Prosecutors 2013* s 4.4.

4. Age of the suspect;
5. Impact on the community;
6. Proportionality of response through prosecution (incl. issues of cost and effective case management);
7. Involvement of sources on information that need protection.¹⁰⁷

In more serious cases, where the suspect presents a substantial bail risk and not all the evidence is available at the time when he or she must be released from custody unless charged, the Full Code Test might not be appropriate, because not all evidence has yet been gathered. In those cases, the prosecution can use the less stringent Threshold Test. The Threshold Test requires that the prosecution has (1) a “reasonable suspicion” that the suspect has committed the offence; and (2) a realistic prospect of gathering the relevant evidence for ensuring a conviction.¹⁰⁸

The CPS publishes yearly “caseload” data which might suggest the proportion of cases that are referred by the police but which nonetheless do not pass the Full Code Test. The problem with the data is that it’s not clear if the “pre-charge decisions” are the same ones as the police “out of court disposals” already presented in Figure 7, or if they are those who were not disposed by the police, but instead referred to the CPS, and the CPS decided not to proceed with the charge. This might suggest that, out of the cases police officers are referring to prosecutors, yet another third is discarded through pre-charge decisions or out of court disposals. The other two thirds (about 760,000 cases yearly) proceed to court. The trend in the data also suggests that the CPS caseload has declined consistently in the past decade.¹⁰⁹

¹⁰⁷ *ibid* 4.12.

¹⁰⁸ *ibid* 5.1-11.

¹⁰⁹ Crown Prosecution Service, ‘Crown Prosecution Service Caseload Data’ (2016) <http://www.cps.gov.uk/data/annual_report/ar2016.html> accessed 23 November 2016.

Figure 9: Crown Prosecution Service Caseload Data between 2007 and 2016.

1.3. In-court settlement: encouraging early guilty pleas

The first potential meaning of court-encouraged settlement in criminal justice can refer to the powers the English judge has in getting the prosecution and the defendant to settle on an outcome. Influenced by the Woolf reforms, the current Criminal Procedure Rules direct the judge to “encourage the participants to co-operate in the progression of the case”,¹¹⁰ and he is bound to attempt to conclude the case at each hearing.¹¹¹ The Plea and Case Management Hearing (PCMH) is a powerful structure that offers three incentives for conflict resolution.

Firstly, the judge is specifically instructed by the rules to settle as many issues as possible so as to minimize the number of hearings required.¹¹² In addition, the parties also have a corresponding duty to “actively assist the court in fulfilling its duty”, for

¹¹⁰ The Criminal Procedure Rules 2015 2015 s 3.2.(2).(g).

¹¹¹ *ibid* 3.9.

¹¹² Plea and Case Management Hearing Form: Guidance Notes 2011 2011.

instance, by communicating at first available opportunity, and all throughout the case, including regarding 1) the guilty plea; and 2) issues of agreement/dispute.¹¹³

Secondly, the PCMH gives the defendant a key opportunity to **enter a plea**, and the sentence is typically discounted so as to encourage defendants to plead guilty at the earliest opportunity. According to the current sentencing guidelines, a guilty plea discounts the sentence by 1/3 if given at the “first reasonable opportunity”, by 1/4 after a trial date is set, and 1/10 after the trial has begun.¹¹⁴ These discounts are currently under review, and the new sliding scale tries to increase the number of early guilty pleas in front of the judge (by offering 1/3 discount for defendants who plead guilty the first time they are asked by the court during PCMH) and discourage late pleas (by offering 1/10 on the first day of trial and no discount afterwards).¹¹⁵

The 2009 Guidelines on the acceptance of pleas and the prosecutor's role in the sentencing exercise indicates that the prosecutor has to take into account the victim's interest when negotiating a plea, and that the plea bargain should not be illogical or unsupported as it can be overturned.¹¹⁶ The guidelines also explain what happens when the prosecutor agrees with the written basis of the plea submitted by the defence or when the two parties do not agree; in the latter case, a Newton Hearing is needed to allow the judge to adjudicate which is the appropriate basis of the plea.¹¹⁷ In all cases, the plea has to be approved by the trial judge.¹¹⁸

Thirdly, during the PCMH the defendant can ask the judge for an **early indication of the sentence** to be given in that particular case.¹¹⁹ This indication, very similar to the Early Neutral Evaluation in civil cases, can be a powerful settlement instrument as it offers the defendant important additional information in considering his plea – namely,

¹¹³ Criminal Practice Directions 2015 2015 s 3.3.

¹¹⁴ Sentencing Guidelines Council, Reduction in Sentence for a Guilty Plea (Revised) 2007 7.

¹¹⁵ BBC News, 'Prison Sentences: Plans "to Encourage" Early Guilty Pleas' *BBC News* (11 February 2016) <<http://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-35539185>> accessed 23 November 2016.

¹¹⁶ Crown Prosecution Service, 'Guidelines on the Acceptance of Pleas and the Prosecutor's Role in the Sentencing Exercise' (2009) s A1 and A3 <<https://www.gov.uk/guidance/the-acceptance-of-pleas-and-the-prosecutors-role-in-the-sentencing-exercise>> accessed 13 August 2016.

¹¹⁷ *ibid* C8 and C9.

¹¹⁸ *ibid* C10.

¹¹⁹ Health and Safety Executive, 'At the Crown Court - Court Stage - Enforcement Guide (England & Wales)' para 9 <http://www.hse.gov.uk/enforce/enforcementguide/court/crown-court.htm#P1_33> accessed 29 November 2015.

what maximum sentence he would get if pleading guilty, as opposed to the sentence more likely to be awarded if he were convicted on trial.¹²⁰

The early indication used to be an informal practice in English criminal court up until *R v Turner* [1970], when the Court of Appeal (Criminal Division) considered an appeal where the defendant had entered a plea of guilty, but had felt himself under undue pressure from the judge. The court urged caution in the practice of counsel seeing the judge in his chambers; and, most importantly, it also disallowed sentence indications, especially in informal settings such as the judge's chambers.¹²¹ *Turner* was later overturned by *Goodyear* in 2005, which established certain conditions that ensure no improper pressure from the judge: the preliminary indication of the sentence from the judge 1) can be requested by the defendant (but the judge can refuse); and 2) if given, it is binding the judge's sentence (maximum sentence); but 3) the indication "expires" if the defendant does not plead guilty following the indication.¹²²

The defendant is personally and exclusively responsible for his plea. When he enters it, it must be entered voluntarily, without improper pressure. *There is to be no bargaining with or by the judge.*¹²³

The early sentence indication is now regulated by the Criminal Procedure Rules.¹²⁴ Sentence indications can only be requested from the judge *after* the basis for plea has been agreed and the prosecutor has consulted with the victim.¹²⁵ Unfortunately, no publicly available statistics on sentence indications exist.

The two figures below present the available data on case outcomes in Magistrates' Courts and the Crown Court, including plea bargains, provided by the Crown Prosecution Service for 2007-2016. The first figure highlights the evolution of the proportion of different case outcomes in Magistrates' Courts. The second figure shows the same figures, but for cases tried in the Crown Court. Plea bargains are coloured in green, and convictions are coloured in red.

¹²⁰ The Criminal Procedure Rules 2015 (n 110).

¹²¹ *R v Turner* [1970] 54 Cr App R 352.

¹²² *R v Goodyear (Karl)* [2005] EWCA 888 (Court of Appeal (Criminal Division)) [61]. Advance sentence indications are also called Goodyear indications due to this case.

¹²³ *ibid* 30 (emphasis added).

¹²⁴ The Criminal Procedure Rules 2015 (n 110) 'Application for indication of sentence'.

¹²⁵ Crown Prosecution Service, 'Guidelines on the Acceptance of Pleas and the Prosecutor's Role in the Sentencing Exercise' (n 116) D.

Figure 10 reveals that the proportion of guilty pleas obtained in Magistrates' Courts has increased over the past decade, from 67% in 2007 to 76% in 2016. If the plea guidelines are implemented, the rate of pleas might increase even further in the next decade. Furthermore, the proportion of convictions is remarkably low (4% of all court cases) and has only slightly increased throughout the years (to 6% in 2016).

Figure 10: Proportion of guilty pleas and convictions in Magistrates' Courts between 2007 and 2016.

In contrast to Magistrates' Courts, the Crown Court has had a remarkably stable rate of guilty pleas (72%) and convictions (8%) over the past decade. This remarkable stability in Crown Court trials and outcomes has been flagged by other authors in the past.¹²⁶

¹²⁶ Kritzer notices the same stability when analysing Crown Court data between 1974 and 2002. (Kritzer (n 5) 748.)

Figure 11: Proportion of guilty pleas and convictions in Crown Court between 2007 and 2016.

Unfortunately, the CPS data does not identify the timing of different guilty pleas – so it is not clear how many of these pleas are made in court, during PCMH or during the trial. The court statistics throw a bit more light on the timing of the pleas in courts.

Figure 12 below presents the timing of guilty pleas in Crown Court cases. The average values have been computed from court data from 2010 to 2016.¹²⁷ The first 6 values (in different shades of blue) represent the number of pre-trial hearings (i.e. pleas entered “at plea, at the plea and case management hearing or at a newton hearing (no further trial time required)”). The value coloured in grey represents the “cracked trials” due to plea – namely, the cases where the trial date was set but it did not take place because the defendant chose to plead guilty right before or on the day of the trial. The red variable represents the number of pleas taken during the trial.

¹²⁷ UK Ministry of Justice, ‘Criminal Court Statistics - Datasets’ (2016) <<https://data.gov.uk/dataset/criminal-court-statistics>> accessed 23 November 2016 Table C7 ‘Defendants dealt with¹ in trial cases where a guilty plea was entered before, during or at a cracked trial, and accepted in the Crown Court, by receipt type, England and Wales, annually 2010 - 2016’.

Figure 12: Timing of pleas in Crown Court cases - average values.

The figure reveals that more than two thirds of pleas take place long before a trial date is set, in one of the preliminary hearings (74% either-way, 70% indictable). Moreover, for the majority of either-way offences, the defendant enters a plea at the first hearing, most probably the PCMH (53%). This might suggest judicial pressure combined with the incentive to obtain a significant sentence discount by pleading sooner rather than later. The figure also reveals that almost no plea is entered once the trial has started (1%).

An early plea does not just discount the sentence significantly, but it also significantly decreases the waiting times for criminal trials and it significantly shortens the Crown Court hearing themselves. The figures computed for the past 16 years show that the average waiting time for a defendant who pleaded guilty is almost half (12.3 weeks) than one who pleaded not guilty (23.4 weeks). In addition, the hearings themselves are almost ten times shorter for defendants who plead guilty (1.4 hours) than those who plead not guilty (12.4 hours).¹²⁸ In other words, a guilty plea is most often translated into a speedy resolution of the case, less hassle for the victims and the witnesses, less effort invested by the prosecution and the counsel, and less expenditure for the justice system.

Unfortunately, the data available is not as detailed for Magistrates' Courts. The only useful data in determining when pleas are entered once the case enters the court system can be found in "key reasons for cracked magistrates' court' trials". A cracked trial is a trial that has been set, but then on the day of the hearing the trial does not take

¹²⁸ ibid Table C10 'Average hearing¹ and waiting² times for trial cases³ in the Crown Court by plea in England and Wales, annually 2000 - 2016'.

place, for various reasons, including the situation where the defendant has decided to plead guilty.

Figure 13: Reasons for cracked trials in Magistrates' Courts (averages from between 2010 to 2016).

Figure 13 reveals that in 38% of cases where a trial date has been listed, the trial “cracks”, in majority of cases because of a late plea (52%), because the prosecution has decided to end the case (40%), or because the defendant has pleaded guilty to a new charge put forward by the prosecution (7%).

1.3. In court: managing prosecutorial actions

In addition to her direct rapport with the defendant, the judge also controls some of the actions of the prosecution in pursuing or settling the case. First, if the prosecutor decides to withdraw an offence before a plea was taken, leave has to be granted by the court.¹²⁹ These actions account for 15% of the cracked trials in Magistrates' Courts, as Figure 13 suggests (see category “prosecution ends case”).

Secondly, a new instrument called Deferred Prosecution Agreements (DPA) can be seen as an instrument of negotiation between the prosecution and the defendant, and the judge has extensive powers in allowing, monitoring and suspending the agreement.¹³⁰

¹²⁹ The Crown Prosecution Service, ‘Termination of Proceedings: Legal Guidance’ <http://www.cps.gov.uk/legal/s_to_u/termination_of_proceedings/#a03> accessed 8 February 2016.

¹³⁰ The Criminal Procedure Rules 2015 (n 110).

The DPA is a very unusual instrument and thus it was first employed in an English court only recently, in November 2015.¹³¹

¹³¹ *SFO v Standard Bank* (Queen's Bench Division).

CONCLUSIONS: REASONS FOR PROMOTING SETTLEMENT

In the United Kingdom, the official discourse used to promote settlement uses different rationales for civil cases as opposed to criminal cases. This is most invariably due to the different aims and characteristics of civil and criminal cases. In civil justice, “dispute resolution” is one of the core reasons why litigants end up going to court. For that reason, in civil justice, the preliminary mapping so far suggests that the main reasons for promoting settlement are:

1. The excessive cost of court litigation. In the UK, the wide majority of fees charged by lawyers are not conditional upon winning the case, but charged on an hourly basis, accrue as the case proceeds through the justice system, and are relatively high and disproportionate to the value of the case.¹³² Genn’s 1996 review of civil litigation costs in High Court cases revealed that in 40% of lowest value cases the costs *on one side alone* were close to or *exceeded* the total value of the claim.¹³³ Genn also demonstrated that the complexity of cases increase their cost, irrespective of the type of case.¹³⁴ The comparatively high costs of lawyer fees are partly explainable by the adversarial character of English justice, as opposed to civil jurisdictions which operate within an inquisitorial framework and, thus, give judges “more work” to do. The latter entails that, in civil jurisdictions, court fees are the major component of litigation costs, while in common law jurisdictions, lawyer and expert fees constitute the major component.¹³⁵ An overview by the European Commission in 2007 reveals that only 39% of the EU countries have lawyer fee arrangements that are not contingent on winning the case.¹³⁶

In the UK there is also a cost shifting principle, which entails that the loser is also liable for paying the winner’s litigation costs, in addition to his own litigation costs. This often means that, if he goes to trial and loses, the loser does not just pay the value of the claim itself, but also the added costs of litigation which often go above the value of the claim. This principle is also found in civil jurisdictions, but these jurisdictions (except for France) “tend to shift costs to the loser on the basis of a *tariff* based on the amount in

¹³² Christopher Hodges, Stefan Vogenauer and Magdalena Tulibacka, *The Costs and Funding of Civil Litigation: A Comparative Perspective* (Bloomsbury Publishing 2010).

¹³³ Hazel Genn, ‘Survey of Litigation Costs’ (1996) para 68. In contrast, in 60% of claims over £250,000, costs represented less than 20% of the value of the claim.

¹³⁴ *ibid* 261.

¹³⁵ Hodges, Vogenauer and Tulibacka (n 132) 5.

¹³⁶ Jean Albert, ‘Study on the Transparency of Costs of Civil Judicial Proceedings in the European Union’ (European Commission 2007) 5
<http://ec.europa.eu/civiljustice/publications/docs/costs_civil_proceedings/cost_proceedings_final_report_en.pdf> accessed 28 December 2016 Annex 1.

dispute. This provides ex ante regulation of the level of costs and a high level of predictability for all parties to litigation.”¹³⁷ The cost shifting principle can be found in 91% of EU jurisdictions,¹³⁸ but not in the United States. In fact, Lord Jackson has made a thorough comparison of the English and American cost allocation rules in his 2009 Review to see whether a move from the cost shifting principle is warranted.¹³⁹

Some authors argue that the legal profession has a vested interest in keeping the cases long and complex, and that, although admirable, any judicial reform is “vulnerable to subversion” by the legal profession if it does not solve the “real causes of cost”:

There are, essentially, three factors which generate the upward pressure on costs: the system of remunerating lawyers on an hourly basis, which rewards complexity; the indemnity rule whereby the winner recovers his costs from the loser, which encourages a competition of investments in litigation; and, the availability of almost unlimited legal aid funds.¹⁴⁰

Although litigation costs are often used as reasons for encouraging settlement at an earlier stage, Genn’s review of litigation costs could not find any evidence that proceedings ended earlier or settled out of court have a direct impact on reducing costs.¹⁴¹ In fact, other researchers have discovered the costs have not decreased, but merely shifted to pre-litigation settlement proceedings.¹⁴²

2. The delay (the duration of cases). The delay of the cases is seen as problematic for 3 reasons: first, because it is inconvenient for the parties (in a non-monetary way); second, because it typically translates into higher costs for the parties;¹⁴³ and third, because it translates into higher costs for the justice system.

¹³⁷ Hodges, Vogenauer and Tulibacka (n 132) 5.

¹³⁸ Albert (n 136) 6 (Annex 1).

¹³⁹ Jackson (n 12) 91-2.

¹⁴⁰ AAS Zuckerman, ‘Lord Woolf’s Access to Justice: Plus Ça Change...’ (1996) 59 *The Modern Law Review* 773, 3.

¹⁴¹ Genn, ‘Survey of Litigation Costs’ (n 133) 271-2.

¹⁴² Goriely and others (n 45).

¹⁴³ For instance, Genn showed that lengthier cases have higher average costs - £8,000 on average for cases not lasting more than one year, while cases lasting more than 4 years end up costing more than £15,000 (ibid 77.). If the duration is translated into stages of proceedings, a High Court case that did not go beyond the issue of proceedings would cost on average £11,000, while one that went to trial would cost on average £34,000 (ibid 79.).

Although delay is normally seen as connected to a higher cost for the parties, the Woolf reforms have revealed in fact an inverse relationship between (1) court delay vs pre-issue delay, and (2) between court delay and litigation cost. Fenn et al. have concluded that:

The Woolf reforms of April 1999 may have achieved its objective in reducing delay in the settlement of litigated claims. However, this achievement may have been bought at the expense of an apparent increase in the delay in settling claims pre-issue (the majority of all cases). At the same time, after controlling for these changes in case duration, it seems that overall case costs have increased substantially over pre-2000 costs for cases of comparable value.¹⁴⁴

3. The concern for litigants in person (LIPs). The prohibitive costs of the English justice system have meant that low-value low-complexity claims are often dealt with by non-represented litigants, or “litigants in person” (LIP). The figures show that 85% of individual defendants in County Court cases and 52% of High Court defendants were unrepresented at some stage during their case.¹⁴⁵ Empirical studies in the UK have revealed that one third of litigants in family cases are LIPs, and in civil cases although most *claimants* (80-90%) are represented, only 15% of individual *defendants* are represented, which suggests a strong imbalance between parties in civil cases.¹⁴⁶ Moorhead and Sefton discovered that self-represented litigants are more likely to miss the hearings, to make errors and to be passive:

Levels of actual activity were usually low. The unrepresented were less likely to defend civil cases; less likely to file formal documents, or make applications; and less likely to attend hearings. They participated at a lower intensity but made more mistakes than represented parties’

¹⁴⁴ Paul Fenn, Neil Rickman and Dev Vencappa, ‘The Impact of the Woolf Reforms on Costs and Delay’ [2009] Centre for Risk & Insurance Studies 26–30
<<https://nottingham.ac.uk/business/businesscentres/crbfs/documents/cris-reports/cris-paper-2009-1.pdf>> accessed 25 September 2016; apud Hazel Genn, *Judging Civil Justice* (1 edition, Cambridge University Press 2009) 56 n48.

¹⁴⁵ Kim Williams, ‘Litigants in Person: A Literature Review’ (Ministry of Justice 2011) 3
<https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/217374/litigants-in-person-literature-review.pdf> accessed 30 September 2016.

¹⁴⁶ R Moorhead and M Sefton, *Litigants in Person: Unrepresented Litigants in First Instance Proceedings* (Department for Constitutional Affairs 2005) 408–9
<<http://www.familieslink.co.uk/download/july07/DCA%20view%20of%20LIPs.pdf>> accessed 23 September 2016.

lawyers (who made plenty of mistakes themselves) and were more likely to make more serious errors.¹⁴⁷

Even more importantly, self-representation seems to bring about poorer outcomes for LIPs in litigation – such as more suspended possession orders in housing cases, more orders for damages (and at higher rates than represented litigants), more frequent costs orders for their opponents, and enforcement was more likely to take occur in their case.¹⁴⁸

Other researchers have discovered that, counterintuitively, LIPs in small claim cases are actually less likely to attempt settlement than represented litigants.¹⁴⁹ Baldwin discovered that this might be due to the mistaken belief of LIPs “that initiating contact with the other side would be regarded by the authorities as improper”.¹⁵⁰ Baldwin thought that it is typically the lawyers that encourage parties to settle, so in their absence LIPs are less likely to attempt settlement, unless there is a judge that actively encourages settlement.¹⁵¹

For these reasons, the existence (and the increase in recent years) of LIPs is a strong reason typically used in the scholarly and judicial discourse for an enhanced focus on judicial interventionism and encouragement of settlement.¹⁵² This becomes all the more pressing after the 2012 enactment of the *Legal Aid, Sentencing and Punishment of Offenders Act* which makes significant cuts to the legal aid available for civil cases.¹⁵³

4. The concern for the flaws of the adversarial approach. In addition to the practical reasons often mentioned in support of a culture of settlement, British scholars often discuss the more philosophical aspect of the adversarial principles of criminal justice and how those should be tailored to the current reality of the justice system. The flaws of the adversarial approach are almost always discussed in tandem with the previous three arguments – proportionality, delay and self-representation. For instance, it is argued that the adversarial approach encourages unnecessary or vexatious litigation, which in turn leads to higher litigation costs and delays. Lord Woolf

¹⁴⁷ *ibid* 409.

¹⁴⁸ *ibid* 410.

¹⁴⁹ Baldwin (n 11) 17.

¹⁵⁰ *ibid* 34.

¹⁵¹ *ibid* 18.

¹⁵² *ibid* 57; Richard Moorhead, ‘The Passive Arbitrator: Litigants in Person and the Challenge To Neutrality’ (2007) 16 *Social & Legal Studies* 405, 406.

¹⁵³ *Legal Aid, Sentencing and Punishment of Offenders Act 2012* 2012.

advocated the need “to bring the uncontrolled features of the adversarial system under proper discipline”,¹⁵⁴and the pre-action protocols which resulted from the Woolf reforms explicitly dictated that “litigation should be a last resort. [...] The parties should consider whether negotiation or some other form of ADR might enable them to settle their dispute without commencing proceedings.”¹⁵⁵ Many post-Woolf empirical studies (summarized in the first section) sought to demonstrate that indeed a settlement culture leads to more proportional costs and less time wasted litigating, but the results are so far mixed. Apart from the “hard evidence”, research on perceptions revealed that indeed a shift in culture has taken place in Britain:

Respondents shared a strong perception that claims were now easier to settle. [...] The perception that settlement was ‘easier’ related to matters other than the trial rate. This was partly because more cases were settled before issue, and partly because it was felt that settlement was more likely to be through discussion of the issues rather than attrition. For example, many housing lawyers felt that the parties now took a more pragmatic approach to resolving matters, and tended to focus on the real issues earlier. In clinical negligence, it may also be that cases are weeded out sooner. Those that survive to the letter of claim stage may have more merit and therefore be more likely to settle. It was also felt that the parties put forward more realistic sums, and were less likely to offer inflated (claimant) or reduced (defendant) values.¹⁵⁶

The flaws of adversarialism are most tightly connected to LIPs. Several scholars have expressed concerns that the adversarial procedures are meant to work optimally when both parties are represented with equal skill.¹⁵⁷ But the unequal representation

¹⁵⁴ Lord Woolf (n 22) 9.

¹⁵⁵ Practice Direction: Pre-Action Conduct and Protocols (n 28).

¹⁵⁶ Goriely and others (n 45) 35.

¹⁵⁷ “A key element in adversarial theory is the neutral and passive judge. It is said that the purpose of the judge’s passivity is to guard against the danger that he might prematurely commit himself to one version of the facts and fail to appreciate the value of all the evidence; in other words, to stop the judge from pre-judging and jumping to conclusions. In this way adversary presentation is seen as an effective way of combatting the natural human tendency to judge too swiftly those things that are familiar. [...] In this way we see that representation and a passive judge are central elements in classic adversarial procedure. The legal philosopher Lon Fuller argues that the integrity of the adjudicative process itself depends on the participation of an advocate. Where a party is unrepresented, without the assistance of partisan advocacy the judge is required to undertake not only his own role but also that of representative for one or both litigants.” (Hazel Genn, “Do-It Yourself Law: Access to Justice and the Challenge of Self-Representation” (Atkin Memorial Lecture, 2012) 10.)

“unsettles the adversarial dynamic of litigation and negotiation”.¹⁵⁸ For that reason, the Equal Treatment Bench Book specifically instructs English judges to assist LIPs by adopting a less adversarial stance, to “adopt to the extent necessary an inquisitorial role to enable the litigant in person fully to present their case (but not in such a way as to appear to give the litigant in person an undue advantage)”.¹⁵⁹

These four reasons presented above are often mentioned interrelatedly in the literature. For instance, the excessive cost of litigation (and the recent decrease in legal aid) has driven an increase in litigants in person, which in turn created a concern about helping LIPs navigate through the system or redirect them to ADR. The duration of cases also typically leads to much higher litigation costs.

In contrast to Italy or Israel, the backlog (i.e. the *amount* of cases) is not often mentioned as problematic. This comparative aspect is perhaps explained by a core difference between civil and common-law systems: on how many cases they allow in the court system and how quickly the cases are processed. The high cost of litigation is often a reason why people do not go to court.

As opposed to civil justice, criminal justice is dictated by different rationales, such as “acquitting the innocent and convicting the guilty”,¹⁶⁰ and its sentences have a more severe impact on the lives of the parties involved. For that reason, the criminal justice system struggles to balance the principles of due process and fairness with those of efficiency, and often efficiency is seen as less important in the face of ensuring only the guilty are convicted and no one, including the innocent defendants, the victims and the witnesses, go through suffering unnecessarily. For that reason, the rationales used in the criminal justice system for encouraging settlement are:

1. Sparing the victims and witnesses the hassle of going through a painful process. In his 2001 Review, Sir Auld argued that judicial settlement mechanisms such as advance sentence indications ought to be used by judges “before putting the public, victims and others involved to the expense and trouble of an unnecessary trial”.¹⁶¹

¹⁵⁸ Moorhead and Sefton (n 145) 409.

¹⁵⁹ Judicial College - England and Wales, Equal Treatment Bench Book 2013 (with 2015 amendments) 2015 s 48.

¹⁶⁰ The Criminal Procedure Rules 2015 (n 110).

¹⁶¹ Auld (n 76) 444.

Indeed, the English court has a statutory duty to “respect the interests of witnesses, victims and jurors”.¹⁶²

2. Sparing the defendant from a disproportionately painful process in cases of petty crime with no serious public repercussions. This rationale has been mostly used in warranting the implementation of out of court disposals applied by police and prosecution, as well as the application of the public interest test for all prosecutions that would normally go to court. Unlike other jurisdictions where the prosecution test consists only in testing the strength of evidence, the English public interest test creates the prosecutorial discretion to not pursue a charge in court if the crime is petty and the estimated consequences of a conviction would be disproportionate. A similar rationale is applied in court mechanisms such as Deferred Prosecution Agreements.

3. Increasing the efficiency of the justice system and saving resources (e.g. minimising cracked trials, the number of hearings etc.). Cracked trials have always been considered one of the measures of the inefficiency of the criminal justice system. The Runciman Commission was worried that 57% of all cases in criminal courts were either cracked or ineffective.¹⁶³ Later, in arguing for the official reintroduction of advance sentence indications, Sir Auld argued that they would “reduce the number of ‘cracked trials’, that is, of guilty defendants only pleading guilty at the last minute”.¹⁶⁴ The Ministry of Justice gathers very detailed court statistics on guilty plea timings, hearings, timeliness of trials, numbers and reasons for cracked trials – which proves that these measures are essential for the evaluation of the criminal justice system’s efficiency.

Unlike civil cases, in criminal cases the *cost* of litigation is never a problem for the parties involved – for the defendant, because Legal Aid is offered in all cases; for the prosecution, because the prosecution has the discretion to only take to court the cases that are “worth” taking from a resource perspective, i.e. pass the public interest test. The cost might nonetheless be a problem for the criminal justice system at a macro level, hence the concern for “cracked” trials and resources wasted in cases where defendants plead “too late”.

¹⁶² The Criminal Procedure Rules 2015 (n 110).

¹⁶³ Viscount Runciman Doxford, ‘Report [of the Royal Commission on Criminal Justice]’ (1993) <https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/271971/2263.pdf> accessed 6 December 2016.

¹⁶⁴ Auld (n 76) 444.

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